

Site: SNHX temple Season '80

Area: N Colonnade Square R16 Locus Number (4)

7/1/80

Progress of Excavation Surface exposed / surface of original rubble fill of S.T. - edge of previous excavation to mound left under large toppled a.b. // 9/12/80: Top of mound of (4) cleared w/ pen knife and small brush. Soil sampled. Frags of alabaster, granite, dolomite chips, mud spots revealed. One large alluvial mud spot (mudbrick?); another frag of tan clay-mud (brick?) similar to that in R2, S, NE (1978). These frags removed - all designated (4) Photographed in color BW before removal. Clearing continues - no change in locus 12:00 C. Zivica works excavation, trowel, pen knife, brush. OVER ->

Locus Description hard packed light brown sand w/ limestone chunks & pieces of what may be yellow mud bricks. This is associated w/ large pieces of limestone. 9/1/80: Alabaster, Granite, Limestone frags. Dark mud spots (alluvial black), tan compact spots. (maybe new level) 10/17/80: More clearing of (4) down to (4a) DARK TAN compact clay for Balk trimming. OVER ->

Location in Square 60 cm East of W. wall of trench R16 to East wall

Under Locus 1 Over Locus Level 2

Locus Dimensions South 1.20 m from edge of W trench

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials Limestone large to small irregular fragments - not particularly chip like, irregular in shape, fairly rounded corners (if struck - then by pounding rather than chiseling action)

④ Sifted with large sieve. Again w/ small 1mm sieve. Samples of 4 as came up from deposit, soil after sifting, also all grades of stone material sampled.

④ Cleared in bulk trimming 10/1/80: sherds put w/ ④ sherds extracted 9/1/80, stone material - granite, diorite, alabaster ~~and~~ inadvertently mixed w/ 4-4a-4b-4c mix by Salah (sifting)

10/1/80: Makeshift Flotation done on ④ sample well water from Salah's house in pan. Little came up - some contamination ^{prob.} from camel's thorn growing in mound. Small black flecks, buff fibrous material.